

Data-Driven Electrification Planning in Nigeria: Identifying High-Priority Regions Using Energy Access Explorer

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Context, Challenges, and Main Findings

- 45–50% of Nigerians lack reliable electricity; rural electrification <30%.
- Rural communities rely heavily on generators due to poor grid service.
- National grid is predominantly gas-powered; solar offers a viable off-grid option.
- Stark regional disparities:
 - I. Low access: Northern states like Kebbi and Yobe
 - II. Higher access: Southern states like Lagos (though uneven)
 - III. Moderate access: North-Central states with underserved rural areas

Transmission & Distribution lines

Research Question

- 1. Which regions in Nigeria should be prioritized for electrification interventions based on population density, infrastructure, solar potential, and socio-economic needs?**
- 2. What electrification strategies (grid extension, off-grids, standalone systems) are most appropriate for different regions based on geospatial data?**
- 3. How can energy access planning be integrated with agriculture, health, and education to maximize socio-economic benefits?**

The Main Findings:

- **Off-Grid Areas:** States like Ekiti, Sokoto, Zamfara, Yobe, Maiduguri, and Taraba show strong solar potential (>1998 kWh/m²/day) and are suitable for decentralized solutions but suffer from poor distribution infrastructure.
- **Healthcare & Education Facilities:**
 - Significant gaps in rural areas.
 - About 33% of the population lacks reliable power for clinics and schools.
 - Targeted solar off-grid solutions can improve health outcomes and educational quality.
- **Agricultural Productivity:**
 - High-potential crop-producing states like Kebbi, Benue, and Niger can benefit from solar-powered irrigation, agro-processing, and cold storage systems.
 - Off-grid systems in these areas are economically viable and can significantly reduce post-harvest losses.

Scenarios

Using the Energy Access Explorer the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Rural clinics and schools	Electrification of rural health and education facilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standalone solar fits low-density, high solar potential regions (GHI > 1998 kWh/m²/day). • Low nighttime light indicates poor electricity access.. • Population density and facility locations are used as demand proxies due to limited real-time data.
Off-grid	Prioritizes off-grid solar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global Horizontal Irradiation (min: 1500, max: 2200kWh/m²) • Standalone solar fits low-density, high solar potential regions (GHI > 1998 kWh/m²/day)

Results

❖ Off-grid solar is economically viable in crop-rich regions:

- High potential in states like Kebbi, Benue, and Niger
- Enhances irrigation, agro-processing, and cold storage

Results

❖ Rural clinics and schools suffer from severe power shortages:

- Affects healthcare (e.g., vaccine storage, maternal care) and education (e.g., digital tools)
- 33% of the population impacted
- Solar-powered systems offer a scalable solution
- Targeted electrification can drive rural development and transformation

Conclusions, Policy insights, & Future Work

Target Electrification by Need and Potential

- **Prioritize off-grid solar solutions in underserved rural states like Zamfara, Yobe, Taraba, and Sokoto, which show both low electrification and high solar potential (>1998 kWh/m²/day).**

Integrate Energy with Social Services

- **Electrify rural health and education facilities using off-grid solar systems.**
- **Focus on states where over 30% of the population lacks reliable power for essential services.**
- **Link energy planning with SDG goals (health, education, poverty alleviation).**

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Leverage Energy for Agriculture

- **Invest in solar-powered agriculture infrastructure in high-yield states to cut post-harvest losses and boost productivity.**
- **Create micro-energy hubs in farming clusters to support agricultural value chains.**

References

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Thank You.